

Extending Online 4D Situational Awareness in Connected and Automated Vehicles

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Abstract—Empowering each vehicle with four dimensional (4D) situational awareness, i.e., accurate knowledge of neighboring vehicles’ 3D locations over time **in a cooperative manner (instead of focusing only on self-localization)**, is fundamental for improving autonomous driving performance in diverse traffic conditions. For this task, identification, localization and tracking of nearby road users is critical for enhancing safety, motion planning and energy consumption of automated vehicles. Advanced perception sensors as well as communication abilities, enable the close collaboration of moving vehicles and other road users, and significantly increase the positioning accuracy via multi-modal sensor fusion. The challenge here is to actually match the extracted measurements from perception sensors with the correct vehicle ID, through data association. In this paper, two novel and distributed Cooperative Localization or Awareness algorithms are formulated, based on linear least-squares minimization and the celebrated Kalman Filter. **They both aim to improve ego vehicle’s 4D situational awareness, so as to be fully location aware of its surrounding and not just its own position.** For that purpose, ego vehicle forms a star like topology with its neighbors, and fuses four types of multi-modal inter-vehicular measurements (position, distance, azimuth and inclination angle) via the linear Graph Laplacian operator and geometry capturing differential coordinates. Moreover, a data association strategy has been integrated to the algorithms as part of the identification process, which is shown to be much more beneficial than traditional Hungarian algorithm. An extensive experimental study has been conducted in CARLA, SUMO and Artery simulators, highlighting the benefits of the proposed methods in a variety of experimental scenarios, and verifying increased situational awareness ability. The proposed distributed approaches offer high positioning accuracy, outperforming other state-of-the-art centralized and distributed methods.

Index Terms—4D Situational Awareness, Localization, Multi-modal sensor fusion, Data association

I. INTRODUCTION

Localization of mobile agents, as an indispensable and distinctive part of situational awareness [1], has emerged

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as highly significant task [2]–[7] in Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS), Internet of Things, Robotics, Wireless Sensor Networks, etc. Major applications such as navigation, surveillance, exploration and mapping of unknown environments require positioning information, even with *cm* level of accuracy [8]. Especially in ITS, the localization module is a key part of autonomous driving architecture, between perception and path planning layers [9], [10]. Perception, i.e., detection and identification of nearby objects, focuses on traffic scene analysis and understanding using visual sensors (e.g., camera, Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), sonars, etc.), while path planning is mainly dedicated to predict and design vehicle’s driving behavior [11], given its position. However, perception usually misbehaves when complex traffic conditions occur, e.g., night time driving, harsh weather conditions, occluded environments, etc. In that case, many false classifications of 3D objects are apparent. Therefore, 4D situational awareness should be able to remedy the problems caused by these limitations, and extend 3D location estimation or awareness over time much more accurately and with relatively low cost, making autonomous driving cost-efficient, safe and energy friendly. The significance of situational awareness in maintaining and enhancing road safety is further highlighted by the transmission of cooperative awareness messages, which include vehicle’s position among other information, as introduced by related communication standards [12]. In this regard, 5G and Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communications facilitate the close collaboration of autonomous vehicles, transforming them to a swarm of Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) which tackles the automotive challenges in a collective manner [1]. Processing of multi-modal informations, which are exchanged within the swarm, can be realized by two ways: distributed computation at the edge and centralized implementation in richer multi-cloud environments [13]. In this work we adopt the first paradigm, which enables scalability, lower processing time and reliability, proposing novel and distributed Cooperative Localization (CL) approaches in order to realize the vision of distributed swarm intelligence.

Two types of solutions are the most prominent for providing self position information: Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and simultaneous localization and mapping based (SLAM) odometry, using visual and/or LIDAR data. GNSS sensor exploits a constellation of satellites to determine ground position along with Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) control inputs fusion. Limitations related to environmental conditions and mechanical operation [14]–[16] contribute to its low accuracy, exceeding 10 *m* error in urban canyons [10]. In

GNSS denied environments, visual or LIDAR based odometry [17], [18] is preferable. By finding correspondences between some keypoints in successive frames or directly minimizing photometric error using all pixel intensities, the pose of vehicle can be determined. However, in featureless areas or multi-object scenes, they suffer from drift error and fail to produce a pose.

The aim of this work is to formulate and propose novel distributed CL and multi-modal fusion methods for effectively realizing 4D situational awareness task, **which enables efficient ego vehicle's as well as its neighboring vehicles' location estimation**. The swarm of CAVs is treated as an undirected connectivity graph and four multi-modal measurement models, i.e., self position, distance, azimuth and inclination angles, are linearly fused in a compact and unified manner by the Graph Laplacian operator. We explicitly focus on star topologies of CAVs, rather than generic graphs, in order to design distributed and more cost-efficient local awareness solutions. The proposed framework can easily be adopted in other multi-agent schemes like indoor ground and underwater robots, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), etc. We build upon our previous related works [19]–[21], though now extended to deal with more realistic and challenging scenarios. **More specifically, we formulate a collective 3D position estimation scheme, both linear and multi-modal, which enables fully location awareness, instead of just targeting only to ego vehicle's state**, for a swarm of vehicles in a distributed manner. More practical automotive considerations like data association, missing objects detection, dynamic topologies, **quality of network** etc., have been included, highlighting superior performance of the proposed framework. More importantly, our schemes do not require exchange of measurements in iterative manner as in [21], performing accurately enough with much lower complexity. Additionally, we show that the global awareness method of [21] is totally unable to deal with the lack of information about other networked vehicles, whereas our proposed methods remain practically intact.

The main contributions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- We are extending online 4D situational awareness in CAVs, by proposing multi-modal fusion and cost-efficient methods which utilize linear Graph Laplacian least-squares estimation and Kalman Filter (KF). The proposed schemes have the ability to accurately estimate both the position of ego vehicle as well as the positions of its neighbors' in a distributed manner.
- Furthermore, a data association algorithm is included as a key part of the novel methods, which associates relative measurements coming either from LIDAR or camera, to the correct vehicle id (from V2V communication).
- We derive and prove a fundamental limit for the positioning error of each method quantified by the theoretical Cramér-Rao Lower Bound.
- The proposed schemes have been extensively evaluated using realistic traffic patterns generated by CARLA autonomous driving simulator [22] **SUMO and Artery network simulators** [23], [24] in complex scenarios with variable densities of CAVs **and network quality con-**

ditions. Additionally, methods are able to address the dynamic nature of vehicles' connectivity topologies in such scenarios in an efficient manner.

Outline and Notation: Section II reviews related work; Section III is dedicated to system model and preliminaries; Section IV introduces the proposed static Graph Laplacian based method, as well as the data association strategy; Section V presents the proposed adaptive Graph Laplacian based method for situational awareness, and its modification in the case of dynamic V2V topologies; Section VI derives the positioning error bounds attained by the discussed methods; Section VII is dedicated to the experimental setup and results, while Section VIII concludes this work. The notations used throughout this paper are summarized on TABLE I.

TABLE I
NOTATIONS

$a, \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{A}, a(\cdot)$	Scalar, vector, matrix and function
$\mathbf{A}^T, \mathbf{A}^{-1}$	Matrix transpose and matrix inverse
$\mathbf{A}[:, k], \mathbf{A}[k, :]$	k -th column and row of \mathbf{A} , respectively
$\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}), \{a_i\}$	trace of matrix and row vector comprising scalars a_i
$p(\cdot)$	probability distribution function
\mathbb{I}_N	$N \times N$ identity matrix
$\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$	Expectation operator
$\ \cdot\ $	Euclidean norm
$\mathcal{G}(\mu, \sqrt{\Sigma})$	Gaussian distribution with mean μ and covariance Σ

II. RELATED WORK

An overview of multi-modal CL algorithms is provided in [25]–[27]. The related algorithms can usually be distinguished to either centralized or distributed: the former assume the existence of a central node/fusion center which receives from the nodes of the network their measurements in order to estimate their positions, while the latter implies that all the processing and computations are assigned to the individual nodes which interact only with their direct neighbors. To ensure cost effectiveness in terms of resources, computational complexity, scalability, etc., distributed methods are of greater importance. Based on either exploiting or not different motion patterns within a probabilistic framework, algorithms can be categorized also to one-shot and Bayesian tracking. The majority of relevant literature focuses on ego vehicle position estimation, **instead of how accurate can localize its neighbors in a cooperative manner**. However, we will also discuss three approaches very close to the problem of situational awareness. In the following, the related works are grouped into three groups:

- *One-shot or static:* Centralized one-shot algorithm addressing non-line-of-sight distance measurements between the nodes using semi-definite programming is analyzed in [28]. **Multi Dimensional Scaling (MDS)** is a renowned centralized optimization algorithm [29], which through the euclidean distance matrix formulated by each pair of involved nodes, together with their self positioning measurements as anchors, is able to re-estimate accurate enough their positions. **MDS** will be used as a baseline method in this work. Global awareness

of CAVs using e.g., **Graph Laplacian Least-Means-Squares (GLLSM)** algorithm, in which vehicles estimate the locations of the entire swarm utilizing distributed information diffusion, has been introduced in [21] with very promising results regarding location accuracy. The requirement for all-to-all V2V communication at the initialization stage is a limitation that should be addressed.

- *Tracking or adaptive:* A traditional centralized tracking implementation named **Centralized Extended KF (CEKF)** is presented in [2, Chapter 24], in which the vehicles broadcast multi-modal measurements information and control inputs to the fusion center, which in turn estimates their positions using non-linear EKF algorithm. State-of-the art message passing sum product algorithm over wireless network which exploits only the relative inter-nodes distances is presented in [26]. Message passing are probabilistic algorithms which exhibit tracking properties though at the cost of high number of iterations. Cooperative localization in underwater environments is discussed in [30], where the state of autonomous underwater vehicle is augmented, apart from 2D position, with the yaw angle parameter. To address the possible non-Gaussian measurement noise of yaw in this harsh environment, a robust two-stage Cubature KF is introduced. The authors of [31] developed a distributed probabilistic CL method for localizing vehicles in the presence of non-line-of-sight range measurements and malicious (from cyber-attacks) vehicles. However, they focused mainly on ego vehicle location's estimation. A distributed CL using KFs named **Multi Sensor Multi Vehicle Localization (MSMV)** is discussed in [32], where ego vehicle estimates its self position exploiting the so-called local and global filters. Each local filter corresponds to a KF, which in turn makes use of two types of measurements: i) self GNSS and IMU, ii) measurements received by the connected neighbors. These two types of measurements represent in fact the position of ego vehicle measured by itself and its neighbors. An optimal weighting and fusion of the individual local filters is provided in order to derive the global filter based on the assumption of Gaussian measurement noise. Since we propose a relatively similar framework, the method of [32] is also included in the evaluation study of Section VII.

- *Situational awareness like approaches:* Covariance intersection has been employed in the situational awareness scenario of a multi-robot group in [33]. Each robot makes use of an EKF, exploiting relative observations to landmarks and other robots. Although covariance intersection ensured communication resilience and estimation consistency, the evaluation has been performed in a rather undynamic indoor environment, with fixed communication topologies. Improving standalone GNSS accuracy is discussed in [10] and [34]. Vehicles detect from LIDAR non-cooperative features and extract relative measurements. These Vehicle-to-Feature measurements, with perfect or not data association, along with GNSS are fed into a KF in order to estimate vehicle's location. Both methods are close enough to realize situational awareness

task, though exhibiting some drawbacks: i) collaborating vehicles have to reach a consensus on features' positions, consuming additional communication resources and ii) authors don't evaluate how accurate the locations of nearby objects are estimated.

III. 4D SITUATIONAL AWARENESS: SYSTEM MODEL AND PRELIMINARIES

The problem at hand and system model will be presented in this Section. As a preliminary solution, an EKF based distributed scheme will be formulated, with individual pairwise multi-modal measurements as its key feature.

A. System model

Consider some sensor-rich CAVs moving in an urban environment (see Fig. 1), which may extract measurements and exchange relevant messages. These autonomous ground vehicles are members of the cluster (or swarm) $\mathcal{C}^{(t)}$ at time instant t , with cardinality $|\mathcal{C}^{(t)}|$. Vehicles communicate with other nearby vehicles (links of the swarm) only within a direct communication range r_c , according to established V2V communication standards [12]. Although in practice r_c reaches 200–300m, in this work communication range is much lower, i.e., between 20–40m, so as to reduce computational load though without compromising the accuracy. Vehicles could adopt a multiple access like communication protocol. Swarm's members are at the same time equipped with a multitude of advanced perception sensors, including cameras, LIDAR, RADAR, GNSS, etc., contributing in providing situational awareness with respect to self and neighboring vehicles' states. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Deep Learning [35], [36] are considered paramount for effectively realizing this task. The extracted scene analysis and understanding indicators, in the form of relative inter-vehicular measurements with respect to the centroids of detected bounding boxes, are further exploited by each vehicle in order to increase its overall 4D situational awareness. We have to point out that an effective data association step is imperative for vehicle i to match the relative measurements coming from its own perception system to correct vehicle j (with ID from V2V). This aspect is explicitly discussed in Section IV.

Fig. 1. Cluster or swarm of four ground connected and automated vehicles. Bold red links indicate V2V connections

State of vehicle i at time instant t is denoted as $x_i^{(t)} = [x^{(t)} \ y^{(t)} \ z^{(t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, comprising 3D position of i . As

for the dynamics of i 's state with dt time interval, the state transition model can be written as:

- State dynamics:

$$\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} = f(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t-1)}, \mathbf{u}_i^{(t)}) + \mathbf{w}_i^{(t)}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)}})$. Function $f(\cdot)$ in general may take a linear or non-linear form (with respect to state vector) according to the chosen kinematic model [37], namely Constant Velocity (CV), Constant Turn Rate and Velocity (CTRV) or Constant Turn Rate and Acceleration (CTRA). For example, in CV motion model, function f is equal to: $f = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_i^{(t-1)} +$

$\mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_i^{(t)}$, where $\mathbf{A} = \mathbb{I}_3$ and $\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} dt & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & dt & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & dt \end{bmatrix}$. The control

input vector $\mathbf{u}_i^{(t)} = [u_i^{(x,t)} \quad u_i^{(y,t)} \quad u_i^{(z,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ comprises 3D velocity as measured by IMU sensor. The other models consider parameters like angular velocity, yaw angle and acceleration in order to physically approximate the motion of vehicle. Approaches such as visual or LIDAR based odometry [17], [18], GNSS/IMU fusion, etc., provide noisy estimations of self state. Note that different positioning solutions should be aligned in the same reference system. Additionally, visual sensors through 2D and 3D object detection methods extract relative observation measurements towards nearby objects, modelled by a deterministic relative location function h which can be range, angle or their combinations. Formally speaking, two types of multi-modal and heterogeneous measurements are available to vehicle i :

- Self positioning measurement:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{n}_p, \mathbf{n}_p \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \Sigma_p) \quad (2)$$

- Relative observation measurement:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{o,ij}^{(t)} = h(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}) + \mathbf{n}_o, \mathbf{n}_o \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sigma_o) \quad (3)$$

Considering relative distance, azimuth and inclination angles ($o = \{d, az, in\}$), h will be equal to: $z_{d,ij}^{(t)} = \|\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}\|$, $z_{az,ij}^{(t)} = \arctan2(y_j^{(t)} - y_i^{(t)}, x_j^{(t)} - x_i^{(t)})$ ¹ and $z_{in,ij}^{(t)} = \arccos \frac{z_j^{(t)} - z_i^{(t)}}{\|\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}\|}$, respectively. Figure 2 graphically illustrates the discussed quantities. In practice, relative observations are measured in the LIDAR reference plane of i using the centroids of 3D detected bounding boxes of nearby vehicles. Sensor uncertainties are modelled by adding Gaussian noise to individual measurements, as indicated in relevant literature [7], [25], [39].

Through a non-linear transformation the traditional non-linear measurements models turn into linear ones, as shown in [21]. By extending this transformation to the 3D case, the

differential coordinates $\mathbf{z}_{\delta,i}^{(t)} = [z_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} \quad z_{\delta,i}^{(y,t)} \quad z_{\delta,i}^{(z,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ will be equal to:

$$z_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} x_i^{(t)} - x_j^{(t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \cos z_{az,ij}^{(t)} \sin z_{in,ij}^{(t)} \quad (4)$$

$$z_{\delta,i}^{(y,t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} y_i^{(t)} - y_j^{(t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin z_{az,ij}^{(t)} \sin z_{in,ij}^{(t)} \quad (5)$$

$$z_{\delta,i}^{(z,t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} z_i^{(t)} - z_j^{(t)} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \cos z_{in,ij}^{(t)}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ is the neighborhood of i (including i). In practice, vector $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)} = [\tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} \quad \tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(y,t)} \quad \tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(z,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is measured by vehicle i , using the relative observations of (3). Section IV will demonstrate that differential coordinates are also degraded by Gaussian noise.

In the context of 4D situational awareness, ego vehicle i is willing to estimate its position along with the positions of vehicles belonging to its neighborhood, in a distributed manner and over time (fourth dimension). This group of collaborating vehicles makes up a star like V2V topology. Formally speaking, vehicle i seeks to estimate its state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = \left[\overbrace{x_i^{(t)} \dots x_j^{(t)}}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \quad \overbrace{y_i^{(t)} \dots y_j^{(t)}}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \quad \overbrace{z_i^{(t)} \dots z_j^{(t)}}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \right]^T, \quad (7)$$

which contains the 3D positions of itself and nearby connected vehicles, in a cost effective and efficient manner in order to be fully location-aware and maximize its driving performance.

Fig. 2. Relative observations of i towards j in 3D space

B. Preliminary adaptive solution

Before we proceed with the proposed novel solutions, we will shortly review an already developed distributed non-linear approach for situational awareness estimation [20], named **EKF for situational awareness** or **EKF-SA**, in which we integrated the inclination angle measurement and replaced yaw angle parameter with z -direction position in the target state vector. The following state-space model was used to derive the solution:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t-1)}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^{(t)}) + \hat{\mathbf{w}}_i^{(t)}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{w}}_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)}}) \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(t)} = g(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}) + \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{n}}_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)}}) \quad (9)$$

¹See the definition of $\arctan2(\cdot)$ in [38, Chapter 5]

Under such a formulation, the well-known EKF algorithm, a sub-optimal Bayesian Minimum Mean Square Estimator (MMSE), was employed. The latter treats the positioning problem as a probabilistic inference task, integrating also a mobility model, and returns a set of possible locations leading to a more direct representation of the solution quality.

Dynamics function f follows the CV model of (1), i.e., $f = \mathbf{A}_i \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{B}_i \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^{(t)}$, with control input vector $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ containing the 3D velocity of i and its neighbors, while state covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times 3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$. Measurement vector $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|+3}$ consists of all the relative observations (distance, azimuth and inclination angle) of i towards neighbors and vice versa, as well as the 3D positions of neighborhood. Function g is defined in the same manner, following the definitions of distance, azimuth, inclination and positioning models. Measurement covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|+3) \times (6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|+3)}$. Non-linear and pair wise relative and self measurements are used in this method, without considering any other type of connection properties among the CAVs. Note that neighbors estimate and transmit in fact a vector of relative measurements since they have their own neighbors. Thus, ego vehicle has to find the "correct" relative measurements of neighbors which match to itself (data association). We have to point out that in realistic traffic conditions, V2V topologies are dynamic since new vehicles may enter or exit them according to their r_c . However, in those cases EKF has to be dynamically reset since the state vector is no longer the same as before. The adaptability to modifying topologies is further discussed in Section V-B. Notice that due to the non-linearity of (9), EKF approximates function g via Taylor expansion, using the corresponding Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{H}_i^{(t)}$ with respect to motion predicted state. Exactly due to this non-linearity, EKF is a sub-optimal estimator. In the following, we will demonstrate how the multi-modal self and relative measurements can be combined within a linear framework, which actually describes the connectivity links of CAVs, leading to much more accurate and cost efficient solutions.

IV. STATIC GRAPH LAPLACIAN SITUATIONAL AWARENESS AND DATA ASSOCIATION

In this Section, the proposed distributed Graph Laplacian static localization scheme aiming to 4D situational awareness will be derived, based on linear least-squares minimization. Differential coordinates which capture the geometry of star topology and integrate the measurement models are fused using the linear Graph Laplacian operator. In addition, an efficient algorithm for matching the relative measurements coming from visual sensors with the correct vehicle's ID from V2V communication, will be provided.

A. Linear least-squares estimation

The goal here is to define and minimize a strongly convex risk function $\mathcal{J}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})$, assigned to each individual vehicle and conditioned over the available measurement vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$. Minimizing this convex function enables vehicle i to perform

the location estimation task quite fast and reliable. Risk function J will take the form of an affine function

$$J(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}) = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}, \quad (10)$$

for some modelling matrix $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}$.

Consider a star graph depicting the neighborhood $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$, with i at its center and every $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ at its leaf. For this star graph, the local Laplacian matrix $\mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ encodes the connectivity links of vehicles belonging to the specific neighborhood and is equal to: $\mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} = \mathbf{D}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{V}_i^{(t)}$, where $\mathbf{D}_i^{(t)}, \mathbf{V}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ are the degree and adjacency matrices [40]. For example, when $|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| = 4$ then

$$\mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -1 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \text{ Note that the first row would}$$

actually correspond to the i -th line of the Laplacian matrix of the entire swarm of vehicles, if we employed a related centralized based algorithm [21]. This fact means that a star based representation enables ego position estimation almost as accurate as if we had knowledge about the entire swarm, but with much lower computational cost. Additionally, the inherent geometry of the connectivity graph is captured by the differential coordinates measurements (4)-(6), since they correspond to the barycenter of each vehicle's neighborhood.

Apart from self differential $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}$, vehicle i receives also the differentials of neighbors towards itself, i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,j,i}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(x,t)} & \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(y,t)} & \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(z,t)} \end{bmatrix}^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with $\tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(x,t)} = -\tilde{z}_{d,j,i}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,j,i}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,j,i}^{(t)}$, $\tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(y,t)} = -\tilde{z}_{d,j,i}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{az,j,i}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,j,i}^{(t)}$ and $\tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(z,t)} = -\tilde{z}_{d,j,i}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{in,j,i}^{(t)}$. Once again, i has to perform data association in order to define $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,j,i}^{(t)}$ from the transmitted by neighbor j vector of differentials. Collecting all the available differential coordinates to vector $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} & \{ \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(x,t)} \} & \tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(y,t)} & \{ \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(y,t)} \} & \tilde{z}_{\delta,i}^{(z,t)} & \{ \tilde{z}_{\delta,j,i}^{(z,t)} \} \end{bmatrix}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$, we end up with to the linear system of: $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} =$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}, \text{ with block diagonal } \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

However, due to the singularity of Laplacian matrix, the previous linear system is intractable. To proceed further, we define: the extended Laplacian

matrix $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_i^{(t)} \\ \mathbb{I}_{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times |\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ and local

measurement vector consisted of all available multi-modal measurements (self, relative, differentials):

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(x,t)} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(y,t)} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(y,t)} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,i}^{(z,t)} & \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(z,t)} \end{bmatrix}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|},$$

where vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(x,t)}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(y,t)}, \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(z,t)}$ contain the x, y and z positions of neighborhood, known also as noisy anchor points. Finally, the transformed linear system is now formulated as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}, \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times 3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$. To

solve (11) we need to minimize $\|J(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\|^2$, and therefore from linear least-squares minimization we have that:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = (\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} \quad (12)$$

The proposed scheme is called **Distributed Laplacian Localization for SA** or **DLL-SA** while its main steps are summarized in **Algorithm 1**.

To sum up, we have derived a distributed localization scheme which focuses on 4D situational awareness. Differential coordinates, which capture the geometry of star topology and combine three non-linear multi-modal measurement models are linearly fused with the local Laplacian matrix, which dictates the connectivity representation of vehicles. Ego vehicle defines the associated convex risk function J and minimizes it in a cost effective manner so as to be fully aware of its surrounding. Note that this modelling enables the treatment of measurements and topology in a unified and compact manner which will offer very competitive advantages with respect to **EKF-SA**, as shown in Section VII. We have to point out that **DLL-SA** is inherently different than the distributed method of [19], since the latter focuses explicitly only on ego vehicle location estimation. Furthermore, the usage of noisy anchor points is a major difference with relevant literature, in which the positions of anchors are considered to be known and accurate enough beforehand.

Algorithm 1: DLL-SA

Input: Time horizon T

Output: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$

```

1 for  $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$  do
2   for each ego vehicle  $i$  do
3     Vehicle  $i$  detects nearby vehicles and extracts
       relative measurements ;
4     Vehicles transmit to  $i$  their 3D noisy positions
       and vector of relative measurements ;
5     Ego matches relative measurements to correct
       vehicles' IDs (Algorithm 2);
6      $i$  defines matrices  $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)}$  and  $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}$  ;
7      $i$  defines the local measurement vector  $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$  ;
8      $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = (\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)})^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$  from (12) ;
9   end
10 end
```

B. Data association

The ego vehicle i , having detected the nearby objects using its perception sensors and having measured the relative distances and angles, should subsequently perform the correspondence with specific V2V neighbors IDs. The existing localization methods, do not provide any relevant discussion and rely on the assumption that the ego vehicle i somehow

knows this correspondence. However, in a practical application, a proper mechanism able to provide this matching would be needed. This is exactly the aim of this subsection.

Ego vehicle i receives from its connected neighbors their noisy self positions. In that way the former knows exactly which positions correspond to individual neighboring vehicles. Furthermore, i takes into account measurements $(\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)}, \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}, \tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)})$, should $\tilde{z}_{d,ij} \leq r_c$. Therefore, range measurements from visual sensors larger than r_c are discarded, and consequently the relative measurements would correspond to the available anchor points.

Consider initially the case of **EKF-SA**. Vehicle i has to match each triplet of measurements $(\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)}, \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}, \tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)})$ to the correct ID. Transmitted noisy self positions indicate these V2V links, and therefore i measures the synthetic relative measurements using its own noisy position: $d_s^{(t)} = \|\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} - \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,j}^{(t)}\|$, $az_s^{(t)} = \arctan2(\tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(y,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(y,t)}, \tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(x,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(x,t)})$ and $in_s^{(t)} = \arcsin \frac{\tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(z,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(z,t)}}{d_s^{(t)}}$. Together with the visually extracted measurements, a square matrix is formed comprising the Euclidean distances between synthetic and extracted triplets. Motivated by related multi object tracking approaches [41], [42], the renowned Hungarian algorithm [43] is used for the matching, taking as input the former square matrix of scores. We have to point out that under the assumption that vehicles detect only those vehicles which can communicate with, the proposed Graph Laplacian methods exhibit a competitive advantage with respect to considering distinctive pair-wise relative measurements: no data association is required for computing ego vehicle's differential coordinates, since it suffices to take into account the sum of available relative measurements.

For the case of identifying each $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{\delta,j,i}^{(t)}$ from the transmitted vector of relative measurements, we follow a different strategy. If the Hungarian algorithm is used, we have to match the synthetic measurements to all the available relative measurements transmitted by each one of the neighbors. In that case, the score matrix will no longer be square, and as matter of fact many mismatches will be produced. Instead, we propose a modified approach which reduces the search space to each individual neighbor, in order to increase the possibility of proper matching. A comparative study between Hungarian algorithm and our approach is included in Section VII. More specifically, vehicle i measures the synthetic measurements: $d_s^{(t)} = \|\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,j}^{(t)} - \tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)}\|$, $az_s^{(t)} = \arctan2(\tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(y,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(y,t)}, \tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(x,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(x,t)})$ and $in_s^{(t)} = \arcsin \frac{\tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(z,t)} - \tilde{z}_{p,j}^{(z,t)}}{d_s^{(t)}}$, and then creates vector $\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} -d_s^{(t)} \sin az_s^{(t)} \cos in_s^{(t)} \\ -d_s^{(t)} \cos az_s^{(t)} \cos in_s^{(t)} \\ -d_s^{(t)} \sin in_s^{(t)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Afterwards, since ego vehicle i receives from j the latter's vector of relative measurements, creates the matrix which contains the differential coordinates of j towards its own

neighbors:

$$\mathbf{P}_s^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \dots - \underbrace{\tilde{z}_{d,jk}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,jk}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,jk}^{(t)}}_{|\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|} \dots \\ \dots - \underbrace{\tilde{z}_{d,jk}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{az,jk}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,jk}^{(t)}}_{|\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|} \dots \\ \dots - \underbrace{\tilde{z}_{d,jk}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{in,jk}^{(t)}}_{|\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|} \dots \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Finally, i tries to find which elements of $\mathbf{P}_s^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times |\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|}$ are more similar to x, y and z components of $\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)}$. For that reason, it has to find the minimum value of $\|\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)} - \mathbf{P}_s^{(t)}[:, k]\|, \forall k \in [1, |\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|]$. Should the minimum is determined, column index k would coincide (in the optimal case) with the desired $\tilde{z}_{\delta,ji}^{(t)}$.

The proposed data association strategy correlates anchor points with relative measurements, since self positions indicate the individual IDs of connected neighbors. Obviously, measurements highly contaminated by noise would seriously affect the performance of data association. A similar approach is followed in **EKF-SA**, though instead of differential coordinates, relative distances and angles are treated separately. The main steps of the proposed data association strategy for **DLL-SA** and **LKF-SA** are summarized in **Algorithm 2**, named **Once-at-a-time Neighbor-Wise Data Association (ONW-DA)**.

Algorithm 2: Once-at-a-time Neighbor-Wise Data Association (ONW-DA)

Input: 3D noisy positions, vector of relative measurements

Output: matching of vehicles' IDs with relative measurements

```

1 for  $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$  do
2   for each ego vehicle  $i$  do
3     Vehicle  $i$  detects nearby vehicles and extracts
      relative measurements ;
4     Vehicles transmit to  $i$  their 3D noisy positions
      and vector of relative measurements ;
5     for every neighbor  $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$  in parallel do
6        $i$  computes  $d_s^{(t)}, a_z^{(t)}$  and  $in_s^{(t)}$  ;
7        $i$  creates vector  $\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)}$  from (13) ;
8        $i$  creates matrix  $\mathbf{P}_s^{(t)}$  from (14) ;
9       find  $k \in [1, |\mathcal{N}_j^{(t)}|]$  which minimize ;
10       $\|\mathbf{p}_s^{(t)} - \mathbf{P}_s^{(t)}[:, k]\|$  ;
11       $k$  would (optimally) correspond to  $\tilde{z}_{\delta,ji}^{(t)}$  ;
12    end
13  end
14 end
```

V. ADAPTIVE GRAPH LAPLACIAN SITUATIONAL AWARENESS AND DYNAMIC TOPOLOGIES

In this Section, the proposed tracking based Graph Laplacian scheme will be formulated, based on linear KF algo-

rithm. Noise distribution of differential coordinates is also derived, based on the noise properties of individual non-linear measurements. Furthermore, and exactly due to this tracking framework, a simple yet effective strategy for reformulating the algorithm in order to dynamically capture the varying star topologies will be discussed.

A. Graph Laplacian Kalman Filter

Although **DLL-SA** enables 4D situational awareness in a linear framework, it does that in static and one-shot manner, treating each time instant independently. It would be more efficient for location accuracy to exploit the motion model of vehicles within the estimation scheme. For that purpose, we will resort to probabilistic and tracking based approaches which treat target state vector as random variable, so as to improve solution quality. More specifically, we will show that a tracking approach based on linear KF would actually be preferable against other approaches, such as factor graphs and particle filtering, as it offers good performance at relatively low cost.

Factor graphs optimization is mainly used in SLAM applications [44], [45] in order to perform non-linear least-squares minimization over the current and past robot's poses, assuming Gaussian state and measurement noise. In highly dynamic automotive applications, the involved vehicles are mainly interested for their current locations, including those of the neighboring vehicles. Therefore, the highly costly optimization over all previous locations is rather meaningless in such a case. Particle filtering, a non-parametric belief propagation method [38, Chapter 4], represents the posterior distribution by random state samples (~ 1000) drawn from this distribution, instead of using e.g., the exponential function that defines the density of a normal distribution. Such a representation is non-parametric, and therefore can address a much broader space of distributions than the Gaussian one, making it more suitable for non-linear and non-Gaussian scenarios than KF, though at the cost of higher computational cost [46, Chapter 15]. In the following, we will show that measurement vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$ does follow the Gaussian distribution, and therefore it makes sense to perform tracking via the KF algorithm.

The part of $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$ corresponding to noisy anchor points follows the Gaussian distribution due to (2). For x -differential $\tilde{z}_{\delta,ij}^{(x,t)}$ (the same goes for y and z), we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{z}_{\delta,ij}^{(x,t)} &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)} = \\ &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -(z_{d,ij}^{(t)} + n_d) \sin(z_{az,ij}^{(t)} + n_{az}) \cos(z_{in,ij}^{(t)} + n_{in}) \end{aligned}$$

However, due to mechanical configuration of LIDAR sensors [47], horizontal and vertical angular resolutions are usually small enough. On the contrary, distance measurement noise should not be neglected, due to power emission and especially for large ranges. As a matter of fact, n_{az}, n_{in} will be slightly larger than 0° and thus $\sin(z_{az,ij}^{(t)} + n_{az}) \approx \sin(z_{az,ij}^{(t)})$ and $\cos(z_{in,ij}^{(t)} + n_{in}) \approx \cos(z_{in,ij}^{(t)})$, by trigonometric functions properties. In other words, we can assume that the two angular

components $\sin \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}$ and $\cos \tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)}$ are in fact deterministic quantities. Therefore, x -differential is now equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{z}_{\delta,ij}^{(x,t)} &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)} \approx \\ &\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin(z_{az,ij}^{(t)}) \cos(z_{in,ij}^{(t)}) + n_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)}, \\ n_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} &\sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sigma_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)}), \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma_{\delta,i}^{(x,t)} = \sqrt{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} (\sigma_d \sin(\tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)}) \cos(\tilde{z}_{in,ij}^{(t)}))^2}$ and $\sigma_{\delta,ji}^{(x,t)} = (\sigma_d \sin(\tilde{z}_{az,ji}^{(t)}) \cos(\tilde{z}_{in,ji}^{(t)}))^2$ due to Sum of Gaussians. If we collect all these noise terms to vector $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}$, with diagonal covariance matrix $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \times 6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$ which contains the variances for x, y, z differentials and self positioning measurements of $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$, then:

$$\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} + \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{G}(0, \sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}}) \quad (15)$$

Using the linear Gaussian measurement model of (15) together with the state transition model (8), the linear KF algorithm (now an optimal Bayesian MMSE) is utilized by ego vehicle in order to perform the situational awareness task. The main steps of the proposed **Laplacian KF for SA** or **LKF-SA** are summarized in **Algorithm 3**.

Thus, a distributed tracking scheme aiming to 4D situational awareness has been formulated, based on Graph Laplacian processing and linear KF algorithm. Ego vehicle acts now as the fusion center. It receives from its connected neighbors all the necessary multi-modal measurements and control inputs, defines the extended Laplacian matrix of its own star topology, computes and finally fuses the differential coordinates, in order to estimate its position along with those of its neighbors. **The indicative concept of the proposed approach is shown also in Fig. 3.**

B. Adaptability to varying CAV's topologies

Ego vehicle i forms V2V connections with nearby vehicles according to their communication ranges. As long as the related star topology does not change, i continuously executes e.g., the **LKF-SA**, for 4D situational awareness. However, when nearby vehicles are moving in the opposite direction or perform turn maneuvers, it is likely that after a small time period the star topology will change. This is due to the fact that vehicles exit, enter or both exit and enter the star topology. These three dynamic cases are highlighted in Fig. 4.

In all three cases, **LKF-SA** has to be reset since both the state vector and covariance matrix don't correspond to the current neighbors of i . Instead of initialization with **DLL-SA** scheme, it is more efficient to reformulate the state vector and covariance matrix in order to capture topology's modifications, without resetting tracking's operation. Therefore, a simple yet effective approach is described which offers a kind of adaptability to **LKF-SA**:

- 1) Vehicles exit the topology (Fig. 4-(a)):

Delete the elements and rows/columns of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t-1)}$ and $\hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t-1)}$ which correspond to the outgoing vehicles.

Algorithm 3: LKF-SA

Input: Time horizon T , Measurement covariance $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}$, State covariance $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)}$
Output: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|+3}$

- 1 **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
- 2 **for each ego vehicle** i **do**
- 3 Vehicle i detects nearby vehicles and extracts relative measurements ;
- 4 Vehicles transmit to i their 3D noisy positions, vector of relative measurements and 3D linear velocity;
- 5 Ego matches range measurements to correct vehicles' ids (**Algorithm 2**);
- 6 i defines matrices $\hat{\mathbf{L}}_i^{(t)}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}$;
- 7 i defines the local measurement vector $\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}$;
- 8 **if** $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$ not identical to $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t-1)}$ **then**
- 9 Perform dynamic reset ;
- 10 **else**
- 11 $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t-1)}, \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i^{(t)})$;
- 12 $\bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} = \mathbf{A}_i \hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t-1)} \mathbf{A}_i^T + \hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)}$;
- 13 $\mathbf{K}_i^{(t)} =$
 $\bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} \mathbf{F}_i^{(t)T} (\mathbf{F}_i^{(t)} \bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} \mathbf{F}_i^{(t)T} + \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)})^{-1}$;
- 14 $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} = \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{K}_i^{(t)} (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{F}_i^{(t)} \bar{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})$;
- 15 $\hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t)} = (\mathbb{I}_{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} - \mathbf{K}_i^{(t)} \mathbf{F}_i^{(t)}) \bar{\Sigma}_i^{(t)}$;
- 16 **end**
- 17 **end**
- 18 **end**

- 2) Vehicles enter the topology (Fig. 4-(b)):
Add to $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t-1)}$ the 3D positions of incoming vehicles, using **DLL-SA**. Add to $\hat{\Sigma}_i^{(t-1)}$ new rows and columns with 0's and 1 to the diagonal, corresponding to incoming vehicles.
- 3) Vehicles exit and enter the topology (Fig. 4-(c)):
Combine 1) and 2) cases.

Note that ego vehicle determines outgoing and incoming vehicles according to their individual V2V ids. The described approach offers adaptability to dynamic CAV's topologies to the KF-based solution. In a similar way, **EKF-SA** solves the one-shot optimization scheme of [20] (extended to 3D) using CVX software when a subset of incoming vehicles need position initialization.

VI. POSITION ERROR BOUND FOR SITUATIONAL AWARENESS

It is highly desirable to accurately measure the performance of localization, and in more general, estimation algorithms. For this fundamental task, Cramér-Rao Lower Bound (CRLB) and Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) are necessary. For any unbiased estimation $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ of parameter \mathbf{x} , FIM $\mathbf{I}(\mathbf{x})$ indicates the amount of information the observations \mathbf{z} carry about the unknown parameter \mathbf{x} on average [25]. Let $\Lambda\{p(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})\}$ be the

Fig. 3. Conceptual architecture of the proposed framework for effectively realizing 4D situational awareness solution, based on star graph topologies. Multimodal perception layer exploits 2D image and 3D point cloud fusion to extract relative observations [36]. LKF-SA relies on Graph Laplacian modelling and data association algorithm ONW-DA in order to create matrix $\hat{F}_i^{(t)}$ and vector $\hat{b}_i^{(t)}$. Following the steps of traditional Kalman filtering, i.e., Prediction, Kalman gain and Update, estimates position vector $\hat{x}_i^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|}$. By using the proposed framework, each vehicle ends up to be fully location-aware of its environment

Fig. 4. Cases of dynamic CAV's topologies

likelihood function for z conditioned on x . Then, FIM is given by:

$$\mathbf{I}(x) = -\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \ln \Lambda \{ p(z|x) \} \right], \quad (16)$$

and CRLB is equal to:

$$\mathbf{I}^{-1}(x) \preceq \mathbb{E} \{ (\hat{x} - x)(\hat{x} - x)^T \}, \quad (17)$$

where the expectation is taken over all noise realizations of estimator \hat{x} . If, in addition, we take the trace and square root, then (17) transforms to:

$$\sqrt{\text{tr}(\mathbf{I}^{-1}(x))} \leq \sqrt{\text{tr}(\mathbb{E} \{ (\hat{x} - x)(\hat{x} - x)^T \})} \quad (18)$$

Eq. (17) and (18) simply state that the standard deviation of estimator \hat{x} has lower bound equal to $\sqrt{\text{tr}(\mathbf{I}^{-1}(x))}$ [25]. CRLB can also be used for evaluating whether or not the collaboration of nodes contribute to the improvement of

positioning accuracy. As it is mentioned in [48], collaboration indeed improved position estimates. Therefore, we have to determine the FIM for each one of the discussed methods in order to derive their theoretical positioning bounds.

DLL-SA: For linear least-squares method **DLL-SA**, we have to determine matrix $-\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \hat{x}_i^{(t)2}} \ln \Lambda \{ p(\hat{b}_i^{(t)} | \hat{x}_i^{(t)}) \} \right]$, with $p(\hat{b}_i^{(t)} | \hat{x}_i^{(t)})$ derived from (15).

Proposition 1. Using covariance matrix $\hat{Q}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}$, it is proven that FIM will be equal to:

$$\mathbf{I}(\hat{x}_i^{(t)}) = \hat{F}_i^{(t)T} \hat{Q}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{F}_i^{(t)}$$

Proof. See Appendix. \square

EKF-SA: When KF or EKF are employed, function p from (16) will correspond to the joint probability function of $\hat{x}_i^{(t)}$ and $\hat{z}_i^{(t)}$. As a matter of fact: $p(\hat{z}_i^{(t)} | \hat{x}_i^{(t)}) = p(\hat{x}_i^{(0)}) p(\hat{x}_i^{(t)} | \hat{x}_i^{(t-1)}) p(\hat{z}_i^{(t)} | \hat{z}_i^{(t-1)})$. Given function p and as [49], [1] have already showed, FIM will be equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{I}(\hat{x}_i^{(t)}) &= \mathbf{D}_{i,22}^{(t)} - \mathbf{D}_{i,12}^{(t)} \left(\mathbf{I}(\hat{x}_i^{(t-1)}) + \mathbf{D}_{i,11}^{(t)} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{D}_{i,12}^{(t)T} \\ \mathbf{D}_{i,22}^{(t)} &= \hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)-1} + \mathbf{H}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i^{(t)-1} \mathbf{H}_i^{(t)} \\ \mathbf{D}_{i,12}^{(t)} &= -\mathbf{A}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)-1} \\ \mathbf{D}_{i,11}^{(t)} &= \mathbf{A}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{(t)-1} \mathbf{A}_i \end{aligned}$$

Corresponding matrices $\mathbf{D}_{i,22}^{(t)}$, $\mathbf{D}_{i,12}^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{D}_{i,11}^{(t)}$ are determined from **EKF-SA**.

LKF-SA: In the same way as before, though now using the quantities of **Algorithm 3**, we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} I(\hat{x}_i^{(t)}) &= D_{i,22}^{(t)} - D_{i,12}^{(t)} \left(I(\hat{x}_i^{(t-1)}) + D_{i,11}^{(t)} \right)^{-1} D_{i,12}^{(t)T} \\ D_{i,22}^{(t)} &= \hat{R}_i^{(t)-1} + F_i^{(t)T} \hat{Q}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} F_i^{(t)} \\ D_{i,12}^{(t)} &= -A_i^T \hat{R}_i^{(t)-1} \\ D_{i,11}^{(t)} &= A_i^T \hat{R}_i^{(t)-1} A_i \end{aligned}$$

The discussed FIMs will be further used in Section VII in order to study and evaluate the performance of the three aforementioned approaches.

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this Section, we validate the introduced approaches by performing computer based simulations using Python, **CARLA**, **SUMO** and **Artery** simulators. During the experiments a PC Laptop with 8GB RAM and Intel Core i7-1065G7 CPU @ 1.3 GHz was used.

A. Experimental Setup

Initially, we used dataset ² for Sections VII-B-1-6 and 9, and more specifically Town04 of CARLA simulator with $N = 100$ vehicles moving for $T = 2000$ time instances and time interval $dt = 0.1sec$, without considering the impact of network delay. Every record of the dataset consists of: time stamp, vehicle ID, ground truth position x, y, z in CARLA reference system, ground truth pitch, roll and yaw angles (in degrees), ground truth linear velocity in x, y and z direction (m/s), ground truth linear acceleration in x, y and z direction (m^2/s) and ground truth angular velocity in x, y and z direction (deg/s). For that case, neighborhood of ego vehicle will be created synthetically, considering that two vehicles are neighbors if their true distance is lower or equal than a communication range r_c . Additionally, and only for network delay impact study (Section VII-B-8), using the combined framework of CARLA-ROS-SUMO-Artery, we provide a public dataset³ of 60 vehicles moving for 3000 time instances in CARLA simulator, with driving parameters like 3D position, rotation, velocity, etc. We chose Town01, which resembles a Manhattan grid topology, of the CARLA simulator to conduct our experiments by spawning those 60 vehicles. The synchronization step between the simulators was set to 0.1 sec. As for V2X communication, each vehicle had a transmitting power of 1mW, and the middleware update interval was configured to be 0.05 sec. Moreover, for each one of the agents we provide also the local dynamic map (LDM) along the simulation horizon, as created by SUMO-Artery simulators, which contains the transmitted messages from neighboring vehicles. LDM, a critical service of ETSI standard, is a conceptual data store message containing information which is relevant to the safe and successful operation of ITS applications. Those messages are comprised of neighboring vehicle id, message generation and expiration timestamp, 3D position, speed, yaw and yaw

rate. Given LDMs, we are able to create the neighborhood of any ego vehicle for each time instant, as realistically created by SUMO-Artery simulators. However, in practice the generation timestamp of transmitted LDMs may deviate significantly from current timestamp at which ego vehicle performs cooperative localization. As such, the difference between current timestamp and message generation timestamp will identify the introduced network delay, which will further indicate whether synchronous or asynchronous (partially or fully) data fusion will be performed. In addition, the establishment of ego vehicle's neighborhood will be directly linked with the parameter of network delay, i.e, either all nearby vehicles will be treated as connected neighbors if ego vehicle receives their (outdated or not) LDMs, ignoring the message generation timestamp or individual V2V connections will be established if network delay is below a threshold. Given those assumptions, we have defined four delay mitigation strategies at Section VII-B-8 that will allow us to study the impact of network quality on 4D situational awareness. Apart from the dataset, we provide also a demo video ⁴ which shows in real-time the evaluation of our methods while we drive using CARLA simulator. The integration of the two methods inside CARLA, SUMO and Artery has been performed with the ROS framework. We have chosen two random vehicles along with the swarms which belong to, to conduct the related experiments. The corresponding swarms at four different time slots are demonstrated in Figs. 5-(a), (b). Velocity readings from IMU are degraded

(a) Swarms of 1st ego vehicle (b) Swarms of 2nd ego vehicle

Fig. 5. Swarms of vehicles

by zero mean Gaussian noise, with variance equal to 10% of absolute velocity value, in order to simulate drift error. Conducted experiments study: i) impact of vehicles' number of connections, as dictated by communication range parameter r_c , ii) uncertainty in relative observations and anchor points, iii) data association performance, iv) impact of real-world observations and network quality, and v) execution time. In all cases, both ego vehicle and awareness location error are demonstrated. As for the evaluation metrics, we used instantaneous Location Awareness Error (LAE):

$$LAE_i^{(t)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \left(LE_{j \rightarrow i}^{(t)} \right)^2},$$

where $LE_{j \rightarrow i}^{(t)}$ is the euclidean localization error of j as measured by i . Root Mean Square Error over Time LE (RT-

²<https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/f43v-ww19>

³<https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/511y-4s83>

⁴<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WGmyCKs3o78&t=40s>

LE) and LAE (RT-LAE) are used to evaluate i 's overall ability of performing self localization and 4D situational awareness:

$$RT - LAE_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (LAE_i^{(t)})^2}$$

Furthermore, we constructed the corresponding Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF). Simulation parameters are summarized in **TABLE II**.

Four state-of-art solutions have been employed to evaluate the performance of our schemes, which are already mentioned in Section II: centralized **MDS** [29] and **CEKF**[2, Chapter 24], as well as distributed **GLLMS** [21] and **MSMV**[32]. For comparison purposes, it is assumed that both **MDS** and **CEKF** operate with optimal data association. Furthermore, **CEKF** is extended by adding to the measurement model: relative distances, 3D noisy positions and relative inclination angles measurements, apart from relative azimuth angles. Additionally, the one-shot scheme of [20], extended to centralized case and minimized by CVX, is used when position initialization is needed. Costly **GLLMS** requires K exchanges of measurements between vehicles at each time instant, with K to be increasing when the swarm grows larger, in order to achieve higher accuracy. Moreover, at the initialization stage ego vehicle is required to have knowledge about the noisy positions of the entire swarm. When all-to-all V2V connection or multihop communication is difficult to be established, **GLLMS** is unable to operate. Rate of unknown multihop neighbors (*r.u.m.n*) indicates these missing positions in **GLLMS**. Note that our schemes remain intact from this. **MSMV** scheme ignores the need for data association when nearby vehicles have to estimate the position of ego, and therefore **ONW-DA** is used for this task during the evaluation.

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Number of vehicles N	100, 60 (only for Section VII-B-8)
Time horizon T	2000, 3000 (only for Section VII-B-8)
Updating time dt	0.1sec
$\sigma_d, \sigma_{az}, \sigma_{in}$	1m, 4°, 4°
$\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$	3.5m, 2.5m, 1.5m
r.u.m.n	rate of unknown multihop neighbors
r_c	communication range
α	average probability of successful object detection

B. Evaluation Study

1) *Assessment of motion models*: Initially, we will investigate which one of the motion models, i.e., CV, CTRV and CTRA, is more appropriate for our schemes. As such, function $f(\cdot)$ of (1) will be formulated according to the definition of those models (see [37]). Corresponding motion parameters of vehicles (e.g., velocity, acceleration, yaw rate, etc.) are easily extracted by CARLA. The indicative resultant trajectories of two ego vehicles generated by $f(\cdot)$ are demonstrated in Fig. VII-B with respect to ground truth and 3D velocity over time. Additionally, the $RT - LE$ between ground truth and physically approximated trajectories are summarized in **TABLE VII-B**. It is evident, both from figures as well

as the evaluation metrics, that CV model is more accurate and appropriate for approximating the motion of vehicles in CARLA environment, instead of CTRV and CTRA models. That is because CARLA itself generates the trajectories of vehicles using some kind of well-defined kinematics. In practice, we didn't see any major differences on the performance of **LKF-SA** or the other baseline methods using the different motion models. Therefore, we can assume that e.g., **LKF-SA** is motion model agnostic. In the following experiments CV model will be employed.

TABLE III
ASSESSMENT OF KINEMATIC MODELS IN $RT - LE(m)$ OF TWO VEHICLES

	CV	CTRV	CTRA
1 st veh.	6.25	15.7	8.51
2 nd veh.	6.71	22.75	25.79

Fig. 6. CV and CTRA models with respect to 3D velocity over time

2) *Impact of vehicles' connections*: Vehicles may communicate and establish V2V links with a different number of vehicles while they are moving. Therefore, the amount of relative measurements could be modified and as a matter of fact, it is straightforward to study the impact of network connections to the location estimation accuracy. For this task, three different communication ranges have been utilized, i.e., $r_c = \{20m, 30m, 40m\}$, without imposing any restriction to the maximum allowed number of connected neighbors for each vehicle. The impact of communication range in location awareness and self location error is demonstrated in Fig. 7 and **TABLES IV, V**. First two columns indicate the range of neighborhood's and swarm's size.

In terms of distributed location awareness, we see from both **TABLES** that **GLLMS** with 30 exchanges and a small r.u.m.n equal to 10% of the entire swarm, is totally unable to operate, leading to RT-LAE significantly larger than that of original noisy position source. In addition, it does that in

TABLE IV
RT-LAE (m) VS COMMUNICATION RANGE (1^{st} VEHICLE)

r_c	$ \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)} $	$ C^{(t)} $	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	EKF-SA	GLLMS, $r.u.m.n. = 10\%$	Noisy source
20m	2-10	2-35	3.39	2.35	2.83	6.01	4.47
30m	2-14	2-97	3.62	2.50	3.27	10.92	4.55
40m	2-20	4-145	3.85	2.56	3.46	11.75	4.55

TABLE V
RT-LAE (m) VS COMMUNICATION RANGE (2^{nd} VEHICLE)

r_c	$ \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)} $	$ C^{(t)} $	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	EKF-SA	GLLMS, $r.u.m.n. = 10\%$	Noisy source
20m	2-7	2-26	3.32	2.28	3.02	2.19	4.48
30m	2-9	5-97	3.69	2.51	3.20	7.48	4.52
40m	2-12	6-145	4.00	2.61	3.38	13.72	4.55

Fig. 7. Impact of communication range r_c to ego vehicle's location estimation. Scalability to the growing number of neighbors is achieved with **DLL-SA** and **LKF-SA** First row: 1^{st} vehicle, Second row: 2^{nd} vehicle

a costly manner, since exact time synchronization is needed for these 30 messages. For example, with $r_c = 40m$ in **TABLE IV**, **GLLMS** achieves $11.75m$ while **LKF-SA** $2.56m$, against of $4.55m$ with noisy source. This is due to the fact that **GLLMS** needs reliable information about all other nodes of the swarm during its combination step. Therefore, in the more realistic scenario where no all-to-all V2V connections are apparent, **LKF-SA** succeeds in reducing the RT-LAE of noisy source, e.g., for the 2^{nd} vehicle, by 49%, 44% and 42%, outperforming both **EKF-SA** and **DLL-SA**. Note that as the number of neighbors increases, the task of 4D situational awareness becomes more challenging since new nodes fetch only a single triplet of relative measurements towards ego vehicle. Furthermore, two stages of data association (both for the relative measurements transmitted by the neighbors, as well as those produced by each ego vehicle) required in non-linear **EKF-SA** results in lower accuracy. In the following, we drop **GLLMS** from evaluation since we showed that in more practical considerations it is unable to operate reliably. The CDFs of self location error indicate that scalability can be achieved by both our schemes when the number of neighbors

increases. For example, **LKF-SA** reduced RT-LE of noisy source by 62%, 66% and 69% (1^{st} vehicle), outperforming all other solutions. Centralized **CEKF** and **MDS** with $r_c = 30m$ reduced RT-LE by 54% and increased it by 0.08%, respectively. Noisy anchors and relative distances impact on **MDS**, which requires almost noiseless measurements in order to be accurate enough. It is evident that the proposed distributed tracking **LKF-SA** significantly outperforms all other methods, both the centralized, highlighting the benefits of multi-modal fusion in the context of compact differential coordinates (instead of pair-wise non-linear measurements) and Graph Laplacian operator. We conclude that larger number of connected neighbors improves self location estimation though increases the communication and computational requirements of the distributed solutions. Communication range will be set to $r_c = 30m$, unless mentioned otherwise.

3) *Missing detections of nearby objects*: Relative measurements is a key factor for the success of the proposed schemes since differential coordinates derive directly from them. Advanced visual sensors of LIDAR and cameras capture the traffic scenes and provide fine details of nearby

TABLE VI
RT-LAE (m) VS MISSING RELATIVE OBSERVATIONS (2^{nd} VEHICLE)

α	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	EKF-SA	Noisy source
95.67%	3.30	2.46	3.20	4.52
90.46%	3.45	2.70	4.81	4.52
81.88%	4.07	3.50	7.11	4.52

detected vehicles. Nonetheless, due to a variety of reasons like diverse weather conditions (e.g., sunny, rainy, fog), night time, scattered environments, viewpoint changes of sensors, occluded objects etc., extracted relative measurements may suffer from lower accuracy. The average probability α of correct object detection and classification, derived in [35] for automotive related 3D CNNs will indicate this uncertainty of relative observations. More specifically, with probability $1 - \alpha$ vehicle i is left only with the noisy self position of j and without any relative observations towards him. To investigate the robustness of the proposed schemes, three different values of the parameter α will be utilized, deriving exactly from the 3D CNN of [35] for car class: $\alpha = \{87.96, 90.46, 95.67\}$. The effect of relative measurements' uncertainties in situational awareness is demonstrated in TABLE VI for 2^{nd} vehicle. Accuracy has been decreased with respect to TABLE V, especially for **DLL-SA**. For instance, with $\alpha = 95.67$ **LKF-SA** achieved 45% reduction of RT-LAE of noisy source, **EKF-SA** achieved 30% reduction, while **DLL-SA** 26%. Distributed **LKF-SA** significantly outperformed the other methods. With lower $\alpha = 90.46$, **LKF-SA** and **DLL-SA** achieved 37% and 22% reduction, while **EKF-SA** totally failed to perform since it increased RT-LAE. Finally, with $\alpha = 81.88$ both **DLL-SA** and **EKF-SA** increased RT-LAE of noisy source (over $2.5m$ **EKF-SA**), while **LKF-SA** proved to be once again more effective, succeeding in reducing it by 22%. We conclude that missing detections of nearby vehicles severely impacts the performance of situational awareness. The proposed distributed Laplacian tracking scheme has proven its robustness and effectiveness in a high enough level, reducing RT-LAE of noisy source at least by $1.02m$, explicitly due to the linear multi-modal fusion framework.

4) *Unreliable anchor points*: Apart from the uncertainty in relative measurements caused by harsh conditions, the proposed backend localization framework may suffer from unreliable self positioning information of anchor points. This is due to the fact that standard positioning solutions are highly dependent on environmental conditions (GNSS) and quality of visual data (SLAM). For example, featureless image scenes or tunnels, are prohibitive for SLAM and GNSS based solutions. In these cases, self position is left to be roughly determined by IMU sensor using velocity readings in CV motion model (1). This solution is clearly less accurate than standard approaches, mainly due to the drift of IMU. In this study, we will assume that ego vehicle measures its position using measurement model (2), while the rate of unreliable anchors indicates the number of neighboring vehicles which exploit (1) for self positioning. The effect on 1^{st} ego vehicle location error is demonstrated in Fig. 8. With unreliable anchors equal to 10%, **LKF-SA** achieved 62% reduction of RT-LE of self noisy

source, against 52% with **MSMV** and **CEKF**, 49% with **DLL-SA**, 28% with **EKF-SA** and 0.8% with **MDS**. Our tracking approach outperformed all others, highlighting the benefits of exploiting highly noisy positioning measurements in the compact manner of linear Graph Laplacian. Increasing the rate of unreliable anchors we notice that performances are constantly decreasing. Rate equal to 90% resulted in 37% reduction of RT-LE with **LKF-SA**, 29% with **MSMV**, 44% with **CEKF**, 30% with **DLL-SA**, 2.4% and 3.9% increment with **EKF-SA** and **MDS**. Although **CEKF** seems to be the optimal approach in this experimental case, its performance is actually biased since optimal data association and no time delay between nodes and fusion center have been assumed. Additionally, non-linear and pair-wise measurements based **EKF-SA** actually increased RT-LE of original noisy source. Therefore, we can safely conclude that 4D situational awareness can be realized in efficient manner by **LKF-SA** even when unreliable anchors suffering from drift error do exist.

5) *Data association*: Data association is a key part of the proposed framework. For that purpose, we have evaluated the performance of **ONW-DA** in correctly identifying which relative measurements from neighbors correspond actually to ego vehicle i , against the traditional Hungarian algorithm. Receiver operating characteristics curves are demonstrated in Fig. 9, highlighting the binary classification accuracy. With self position noise variance $\sigma_{x,y,z} = \{3.5, 2.5, 1.5\}m$, **ONW-DA** achieved area under curve (AUC) 0.84, while Hungarian 0.72. This performance indicates that the proposed reduction of search space in order to match the correct relative observations triplet, significantly improved classification accuracy. Increasing self position noise variance to $9m$, both AUCs have been seriously reduced since the synthetic measurements are far away from the extracted measurements. Once again **ONW-DA** is superior. Fig. 9-(c) demonstrates also much greater LAE accuracy with **ONW-DA** than the Hungarian algorithm, since the latter increased RT-LAE of noisy source.

6) *Theoretical positioning bounds and dynamic reset*: Positioning bounds were also used for evaluating 4D situational awareness ability of 2^{nd} vehicle with $r_c = 20m$ in Fig. 10. It is evident from Fig. 10-(a), that the minimum value of CRLB has been attained by **LKF-SA** and **EKF-SA**, proving in a theoretical base the supremacy of probabilistic KF tracking and its effectiveness in terms of location accuracy with respect to least-squares **DLL-SA**. Variations of CRLB values are due to the modifications of individual star topology. For a network of M 2D nodes and as pointed out in [48], CRLB decreases (i.e., lower uncertainty about estimated positions) when the entering node/vehicle introduces at least $2M + 1$ measurements. In our framework, and considering the 2D case, each vehicle needs to estimate $2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|$ positions. When a new vehicle enters the star topology, it introduces 2 relative measurements (distance and azimuth) and its 2D noisy position: a total of 4 values. Therefore, CRLB will be decreased if only $4 \geq 2|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| + 1$. Simply stated, it needs to be $|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}| \leq 1.5$ which is unfeasible. The same goes for the 3D position case. As a matter of fact, exactly due to the formulation of the problem, situational awareness uncertainty increases/decreases should new vehicles

Fig. 8. Effect on ego localization error (1st vehicle) of unreliable self positioning information of its neighbors. As the rate increases, performances are decreased. **LKF-SA** addresses in efficient manner the lack of reliable anchor points against the other methods. **CEKF**'s performance can be considered biased.

Fig. 9. Data association performance of 2nd vehicle. Hungarian algorithm actually increased RT-LAE with $\sigma_{x,y,z} = \{3.5, 2.5, 1.5\}m$

enter/exit the star topology of ego vehicle.

Additionally, we plotted the standard deviation of situational awareness estimation over 500 noise realizations in Fig. 10-(b). The bound of (18) is experimentally proven to be valid for all three methods. Clearly, **LKF-SA** achieved once again the greatest performance. On the other hand, with **EKF-SA** the standard deviation even exceeds 30m, far away from its lower bound, exactly due to applying data association in pair-wise non-linear measurements. This behavior highlights once again the benefits of the proposed multi-modal and compact linear estimation framework

Finally, in Fig. 10-(c) we plotted self LE over 500 noise realizations. It is obvious that **LKF-SA** captures the modifications of star topology, without the need of total re-initialization with **DLL-SA**. Although **LKF-SA** experiences a small increase of self location error when vehicles exit the connectivity topology (due to scalability property), it does that in a dynamic manner and more accurate than **DLL-SA**

7) *Real-world observations*: Apart from the synthetically generated measurements by adding Gaussian noise to ground truth, we believe that there is a need of more realistic experiments in order to extract useful results about the proposed algorithms' performances. As such, we used a public dataset

⁵, which is focused on cooperative localization of four vehicles moving along the same path in Porto, Portugal. For every vehicle, authors collected GPS, IMU and Wi-Fi data using the on-board sensors. For each one of the vehicles and its other three neighbors, we run the proposed 4D situational awareness schemes, integrating the realistic GPS observations from vehicles' sensors, as well as the synthetically generated relative observations using TABLE II, since ground truth position of vehicles is available. Therefore, we evaluate the proposed schemes with real-world GPS data.

Trajectories of four vehicles (Seat, Fiat, Audi and Nissan) are shown in Fig. 12. Accuracy of 4D situational awareness for each one of the vehicles with **DLL-SA**, **LKF-SA**, **EKF-SA** and GPS is demonstrated in TABLE VII. Note that the data association approach of **ONW-DA** has been also integrated. GPS error mainly comes from inaccurate estimation of z parameter. As it can be shown, pair-wise measurements based **EKF-SA** actually increases $RT - LAE$ with respect to GPS by 14%, 10% and 21%. Only for the Nissan car, we see a very small reduction of 0.08%. Using the proposed Graph Laplacian based **DLL-SA** and **LKF-SA**, the benefits in terms of $RT - LAE$ reduction of GPS reach 25% and 26%, respectively, for all four cars. Note that this reduction is significantly smaller than the cases of synthetically generated self and relative observations. For example, in Section VII-B.2, the reduction of $RT - LAE$ reaches almost 50%. Nevertheless, Graph Laplacian based approaches are capable of realizing 4D situational awareness much more accurate than standard GPS sensors, as well as pair-wise cooperative localization approaches which do not capture and exploit the properties of graph topology of connected vehicles.

TABLE VII
RT-LAE (m) OF FOUR CARS WITH REAL GPS OBSERVATIONS

	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	EKF-SA	GPS
<i>Seat</i>	8.52 (−25%)	8.4 (−26%)	13.15 (+14%)	11.34
<i>Fiat</i>	8.54 (−25%)	8.41 (−26%)	12.48 (+10%)	11.34
<i>Audi</i>	8.5 (−25%)	8.38 (−26%)	13.79 (+21%)	11.34
<i>Nissan</i>	8.52 (−25%)	8.39 (−26%)	11.33 (−0.09%)	11.34

⁵<https://iee-dataport.org/open-access/cooperative-localization-vehicular-networks-dataset>

Fig. 10. CRLB, standard deviation and ego localization error of 2nd vehicle

Fig. 11. Visualizations in CARLA environment and heatmaps of trajectory (1st vehicle) using **LKF-SA**. Green texts above vehicles indicate the benefits (in m) of situational awareness against self noisy sources. Multi-colouring of self location error is attributed to the Gaussian randomness of measurement error.

Fig. 12. Ground truth trajectory of four cars (Seat, Fiat, Audi, Nissan), at Porto, Portugal. Vehicles follow the same path at an urban environment and are very close to each other.

8) *Impact of delay*: Evidently, in the previous experimental cases we have assumed that the network of cooperating vehicles is time synchronized, that is vehicles receive and exchange messages of information with perfect network quality. However, in practice due to network congestion, communication resources, etc., network delay should not be ignored. For example, CAMs' generation frequency is between $100ms$ and $1000msec$, according to ETSI standard [12], while the delay of transmission may reach $200msec$ [50]. Therefore, we should expect that during 4D situational awareness, the involved algorithms will integrate outdated data, i.e., received GPS positions and relative observations that correspond to previous time instances. To simulate realistic V2V conditions, we have extended the experimental setup by integrating to CARLA-ROS framework the well-known SUMO simulator, which implements standard V2X communication protocols suitable for vehicular applications. More specifically, the simulator stack shown in Fig. 13, is comprised of CARLA-ROS, which is the component responsible for simulating physics phenomena and rendering, SUMO, which handles the control and coordination

of the simulated entities, and Artery, which is responsible for modeling and implementing V2X communication based on ETSI ITS-G5 protocols and facilitates services, such as CAMs and Decentralized Notification Messages (DENMs). The Traffic Control Interface (TraCI) of the SUMO simulator, which supports interactions with both CARLA and Artery, is responsible of the orchestration of the synchronization of the different components. See more relevant details in [51].

As such, we will define four delay mitigation strategies (DMSs), in order to assess the accuracy of our schemes under realistic V2V conditions, beginning with the case of using SUMO-Artery only for creating the neighborhood (instead of just setting a communication range as we did before) and without considering any outdated information, and the more challenging case of exploiting all the transmitted outdated messages regardless of the delay:

- Delay mitigation strategy #1 (fully synchronous fusion): All the messages are considered time synchronized, and timestamp of message generation is ignored during evaluation.
- Delay mitigation strategy #2 (partially asynchronous fusion): Maximum allowed network delay between current timestamp and generation timestamp of received messages, equal to $100msec$.
- Delay mitigation strategy #3 (partially asynchronous fusion): Maximum allowed network delay between current timestamp and generation timestamp of received messages, equal to $300msec$.
- Delay mitigation strategy #4 (fully asynchronous fusion): We don't impose any threshold to network delay, i.e., all messages are being exploited by our algorithms regardless of timestamp of message generation. The latter indicates

outdated transmitted data, e.g., transmitted GPS position and relative observations corresponding to previous time instances.

A random ego vehicle has been chosen for the assessment of the algorithms, and its trajectory is shown in Fig. 14. Note that the maximum size of ego vehicle’s neighborhood reaches 29, 24, 7 and 29 vehicles, respectively, for the different DMSs, since thresholding maximum allowed delay actually discards V2V connections. Additionally, note that the delay between current timestamp and generation timestamp of received messages introduced by SUMO-Artery simulators, reaches $800msec$. Therefore, it is crucial to impose maximum allowed thresholds. The results are summarized in **TABLE VIII**, for the three situational awareness approaches and noisy GPS sensor. For example, we see that $RT - LAE$ of GPS increases from the optimal to hardest case, since outdated GPS measurements deviate significantly from current ground truth positions. Additionally, pair-wise based **EKF-SA** is clearly unable to reduce GPS error, and is shown to be totally unreliable to integrate greater amount of information from neighbors (DMS #1), as well as to address network delay (DMS #2-#4). Graph Laplacian based schemes, are shown once again significantly robust to this critical challenge. The most efficient out of them is **LKF-SA**, which is shown to improve GPS accuracy by 36%-13%, effectively integrating outdated data (both noisy positions and relative observations). From the fully synchronous towards the fully asynchronous fusion case, we see a decrease on this improvement exactly due to the impact of delayed messages. The improvement of GPS accuracy with **DLL-SA** is between 16%-3%.

Fig. 13. Simulation stack consists of CARLA, SUMO and Artery simulators, on top of which we deploy the proposed 4D situational awareness approaches, through ROS protocol

Fig. 14. Trajectory of ego vehicle during the evaluation of network delay impact

TABLE VIII

RT-LAE (m) VS FOUR NETWORK DELAY MITIGATION STRATEGIES

	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	EKF-SA	GPS
DMS #1	3.81 (-16%)	2.92 (-36%)	4.32 (-5%)	4.56
DMS #2	3.94 (-14%)	3.27 (-29%)	5.47 (+19%)	4.6
DMS #3	4.37 (-5%)	3.87 (-16%)	12.66 (+174%)	4.62
DMS #4	4.56 (-3%)	4.09 (-13%)	14.19 (+202%)	4.7

9) *Execution time*: Instead of how *accurate*, we are also interested in how *quickly* each vehicle performs 4D situational awareness. Therefore, we measured the average execution time of the discussed methods for the two ego vehicles of Sections VII-B-1-6, over time horizon. Timing results are summarized in **TABLE IX**. As you may see, **MSMV** attained

TABLE IX

AVERAGE EXECUTION TIME ($msec$)

	DLL-SA	LKF-SA	MSMV	EKF-SA	CEKF	MDS
1 st veh.	0.90	1.36	0.50	54.19	612.31	1.9
2 nd veh.	0.97	1.34	0.48	43.80	546.39	1.74

the fastest execution time due to the fact that aims only on ego position, instead of situational awareness or whole swarm’s locations estimation. For that reason is omitted from further evaluation. The proposed distributed Graph Laplacian schemes exhibit very attractive results, almost two and three orders of magnitude lower than **EKF-SA** and **CEKF**. This is a very hopeful fact for critical automotive applications which require real-time operation. **DLL-SA** proved to be the fastest due to its simple form. But also **LKF-SA** achieved very promising results. **EKF-SA** and **CEKF** exhibit high enough timing results mainly due to the fact that a costly CVX based solution is employed when new vehicles enter the topology and need position initialization. **EKF-SA** is faster due to its distributed form which considers only the vehicles of the individual star topology. Differences between the two vehicles are caused by the different number of vehicles comprising related swarms and neighborhoods.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we focus on providing ego vehicle the algorithmic tools to perform collective 3D position estimation over time, improving its own self-localization as well as efficiently localizing its direct neighbors. More specifically, a cooperative framework for the problem of distributed 4D situational awareness has been formulated and evaluated. Two novel schemes are proposed, the first one deriving from linear least-squares, while the second one from Kalman Filter. Ego vehicle forms a star like V2V topology with its direct neighbors in order to process and fuse in a distributed manner relative measurements (distances, azimuth and inclination angles), noisy 3D positions and control inputs via the differential coordinates and linear Graph Laplacian operator. Numerical results in CARLA, SUMO and Artery indicate that the proposed tracking method of **LKF-SA** achieved increased effectiveness in the case of varying network connections, robustness against

missing object detections, efficiency in estimating neighbors' 3D positions, and very promising timing results with respect to traditional and state-of-the art techniques. **Additionally, LKF-SA is shown to effectively address realistic network delay caused by V2V communication, significantly improving localization accuracy even if outdated data are considered.** Unreliable anchor points and data association were also taken into account during the evaluation. Our approach should be seen as a backend module, on top of related standard solutions, aiming to robustify traffic scene analysis and improve the accuracy of self positioning. As a future step, the related scene analysis and understanding module will be deployed in each simulated vehicle, in order to extract realistic relative measurements towards nearby objects.

APPENDIX

The likelihood function $\Lambda\{p(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\}$ follows the multivariate Gaussian distribution with zero mean and covariance $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)}$, due to Gaussian measurement model (15):

$$\Lambda\{p(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\} = \frac{e^{(-\frac{1}{2}(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})^T \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} (\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}))}}{\sqrt{(2\pi)^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} | \det(\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)})}}$$

Furthermore, $\ln\Lambda\{p(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\} = \Lambda_1 - \Lambda_2$, where:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_1 &= -\ln\sqrt{(2\pi)^{6|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} | \det(\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)})}. \\ \Lambda_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)})^T \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} (\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)} + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2}\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

As a matter of fact, 1st and 2nd derivative of likelihood function are equal to:

- 1st derivative:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}} \ln\Lambda\{p(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}} - \Lambda_2 = \\ &= -\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} (\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)} - \hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}). \end{aligned}$$

- 2nd derivative:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)2}} \ln\Lambda\{p(\hat{\mathbf{b}}_i^{(t)}|\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)})\} &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)2}} - \Lambda_2 = \\ &= -\hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally:

$$\mathbf{I}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)}) = -\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t)2}} \ln\Lambda\{\cdot\} \right] = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)T} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_{\delta,i}^{(t)-1} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_i^{(t)}.$$

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zhang, R. Pöhlmann, T. Wiedemann, A. Dammann, H. Wymeersch, and P. A. Hoehner, "Self-aware swarm navigation in autonomous exploration missions," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 108, no. 7, pp. 1168–1195, 2020.
- [2] C. Gao, *Cooperative localization and navigation : theory, research, and practice*. Boca Raton: Taylor & Francis, CRC Press, 2019.
- [3] P. S. Farahsari, A. Farahzadi, J. Rezazadeh, and A. Bagheri, "A survey on indoor positioning systems for iot-based applications," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 10, pp. 7680–7699, 2022.
- [4] S. Kuutti, S. Fallah, K. Katsaros, M. Dianati, F. Mccullough, and A. Mouzakitis, "A survey of the state-of-the-art localization techniques and their potentials for autonomous vehicle applications," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 829–846, 2018.
- [5] C. Gao, G. Wang, W. Shi, Z. Wang, and Y. Chen, "Autonomous driving security: State of the art and challenges," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 10, pp. 7572–7595, 2022.
- [6] A. Eskandarian, C. Wu, and C. Sun, "Research advances and challenges of autonomous and connected ground vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 683–711, 2021.
- [7] T. Liang, T. Zhang, J. Yang, D. Feng, and Q. Zhang, "Uav-aided positioning systems for ground devices: Fundamental limits and algorithms," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 15, pp. 13470–13485, 2022.
- [8] J. B. P. Neto, L. C. Gomes, F. M. Ortiz, T. T. Almeida, M. E. M. Campista, L. H. M. Costa, and N. Mitton, "An accurate cooperative positioning system for vehicular safety applications," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 83, p. 106591, 2020.
- [9] U. Montanaro, S. Dixit, S. Fallah, M. Dianati, A. Stevens, D. Oxtoby, and A. Mouzakitis, "Towards connected autonomous driving: review of use-cases," *Vehicle System Dynamics*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 779–814, 2018.
- [10] G. Soatti, M. Nicoli, N. Garcia, B. Denis, R. Raulefs, and H. Wymeersch, "Implicit cooperative positioning in vehicular networks," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 3964–3980, 2018.
- [11] S. Mozaffari, *et al.*, "Deep learning-based vehicle behavior prediction for autonomous driving applications: A review," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 33–47, 2022.
- [12] *ETSI EN 302 637-2 V1.4.1 (2019-01)*, European Telecommunications Standards Institute Std., Jan. 2019.
- [13] P. Arthurs, *et al.*, "A taxonomy and survey of edge cloud computing for intelligent transportation systems and connected vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–16, 2021.
- [14] A. Noureldin, T. B. Karamat, and J. Georgy, *Fundamentals of Inertial Navigation, Satellite-based Positioning and their Integration*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012.
- [15] N. Alam and A. G. Dempster, "Cooperative positioning for vehicular networks: Facts and future," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1708–1717, 2013.
- [16] I. Skog and P. Handel, "In-car positioning and navigation technologies—a survey," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 4–21, 2009.
- [17] C. Chen, *et al.*, "Dynanet: Neural kalman dynamical model for motion estimation and prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 12, pp. 5479–5491, 2021.
- [18] T. Shan and B. Englot, "Lego-loam: Lightweight and ground-optimized lidar odometry and mapping on variable terrain," in *2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2018, pp. 4758–4765.
- [19] N. Piperigkos, A. S. Lalos, and K. Berberidis, "Graph laplacian extended kalman filter for connected and automated vehicles localization," in *2021 4th IEEE International Conference on Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems (ICPS)*. IEEE, 2021.
- [20] —, "Multi-modal cooperative awareness of connected and automated vehicles in smart cities," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Smart Internet of Things (SmartIoT)*, 2021, pp. 377–382.
- [21] —, "Graph laplacian diffusion localization of connected and automated vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–15, 2021.
- [22] A. Dosovitskiy, G. Ros, F. Codevilla, A. Lopez, and V. Koltun, "CARLA: An open urban driving simulator," in *Conference on Robot Learning*, 2017, pp. 1–16.
- [23] P. A. Lopez, M. Behrisch, L. Bieker-Walz, J. Erdmann, Y.-P. Flötteröd, R. Hilbrich, L. Lücken, J. Rummel, P. Wagner, and E. Wiessner, "Microscopic traffic simulation using sumo," in *2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*, 2018, pp. 2575–2582.
- [24] [Online]. Available: <http://artery.v2x-research.eu/>
- [25] R. M. Buehrer, H. Wymeersch, and R. M. Vaghefi, "Collaborative sensor network localization: Algorithms and practical issues," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 6, pp. 1089–1114, 2018.
- [26] H. Wymeersch, J. Lien, and M. Z. Win, "Cooperative localization in wireless networks," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 427–450, 2009.

- [27] S. Safavi, U. A. Khan, S. Kar, and J. M. F. Moura, "Distributed localization: A linear theory," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 106, no. 7, pp. 1204–1223, 2018.
- [28] R. M. Vaghefi and R. M. Buehrer, "Cooperative localization in NLOS environments using semidefinite programming," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 19, no. 8, pp. 1382–1385, 2015.
- [29] I. Dokmanic, R. Parhizkar, J. Ranieri, and M. Vetterli, "Euclidean distance matrices: Essential theory, algorithms, and applications," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 12–30, 2015.
- [30] B. Xu, X. Wang, J. Zhang, Y. Guo, and A. A. Razzaqi, "A novel adaptive filtering for cooperative localization under compass failure and non-gaussian noise," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, pp. 1–1, 2022.
- [31] J. Zhao, Y. Zhang, S. Ni, and Q. Li, "Bayesian cooperative localization with NLOS and malicious vehicle detection in GNSS-challenged environments," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 85 686–85 697, 2020.
- [32] P. Yang, D. Duan, C. Chen, X. Cheng, and L. Yang, "Multi-sensor multi-vehicle (MSMV) localization and mobility tracking for autonomous driving," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 14 355–14 364, 2020.
- [33] T.-K. Chang, K. Chen, and A. Mehta, "Resilient and consistent multi-robot cooperative localization with covariance intersection," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 197–208, 2022.
- [34] M. Brambilla, M. Nicoli, G. Soatti, and F. Deflorio, "Augmenting vehicle localization by cooperative sensing of the driving environment: Insight on data association in urban traffic scenarios," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1646–1663, 2020.
- [35] S. Nousias, E.-V. Pikoulis, C. Mavrokefalidis, A. S. Lalos, and K. Moustakas, "Accelerating 3d scene analysis for autonomous driving on embedded ai computing platforms," in *2021 IFIP/IEEE 29th International Conference on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI-SoC)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [36] S. Nousias, E.-V. Pikoulis, C. Mavrokefalidis, and A. S. Lalos, "Accelerating deep neural networks for efficient scene understanding in multi-modal automotive applications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 28 208–28 221, 2023.
- [37] R. Schubert, E. Richter, and G. Wanielik, "Comparison and evaluation of advanced motion models for vehicle tracking," in *2008 11th International Conference on Information Fusion*, 2008, pp. 1–6.
- [38] S. Thrun, *Probabilistic robotics*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2006.
- [39] M. Elazab, A. Noureldin, and H. S. Hassanein, "Integrated cooperative localization for vehicular networks with partial GPS access in urban canyons," *Vehicular Communications*, vol. 9, pp. 242–253, 2017.
- [40] O. Sorkine, "Laplacian mesh processing," 2005.
- [41] X. Weng, J. Wang, D. Held, and K. Kitani, "3d multi-object tracking: A baseline and new evaluation metrics," in *2020 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2020, pp. 10 359–10 366.
- [42] A. Bewley, Z. Ge, L. Ott, F. Ramos, and B. Upcroft, "Simple online and realtime tracking," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 2016, pp. 3464–3468.
- [43] H. W. Kuhn, "The hungarian method for the assignment problem," *Naval Research Logistics Quarterly*, vol. 2, no. 1-2, pp. 83–97, 1955.
- [44] F. Dellaert and M. Kaess, "Factor graphs for robot perception," *Foundations and Trends in Robotics*, vol. 6, no. 1-2, pp. 1–139, 2017.
- [45] J. Engel, V. Koltun, and D. Cremers, "Direct sparse odometry," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 611–625, 2018.
- [46] D. Simon, *Optimal State Estimation*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2006.
- [47] [Online]. Available: <https://autonomoustuff.com/lidar-chart>
- [48] J. Schloemann and R. M. Buehrer, "On the value of collaboration in location estimation," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 3585–3596, 2016.
- [49] P. Tichavsky, C. Muravchik, and A. Nehorai, "Posterior cramer-rao bounds for discrete-time nonlinear filtering," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 1386–1396, 1998.
- [50] B. Coll-Perales, M. C. Lucas-Estañ, T. Shimizu, J. Gozalvez, T. Higuchi, S. Avedisov, O. Altintas, and M. Sepulcre, "End-to-end v2x latency modeling and analysis in 5g networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 5094–5109, 2023.
- [51] C. Anagnostopoulos, C. Koulamas, A. Lalos, and C. Stylios, "Open-source integrated simulation framework for cooperative autonomous vehicles," in *2022 11th Mediterranean Conference on Embedded Computing (MECO)*, 2022, pp. 1–4.